

Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) Studies of Planetary Materials

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1. Introduction: Raman spectroscopy plays an important role in the identification of planetary materials and for biosignatures. Current Raman instruments for NASA, such as the Scanning Habitable Environments with Raman and Luminescence for Organics and Chemicals (SHERLOC) [1] and SuperCam [2], have been well-matured and integrated into the Mars 2020 space mission. Major improvements in the capabilities of such systems are desired, particularly enabling them to perform ultrasensitive measurements and detect life and habitability in outer space. Essentially, there is a need to develop a next-generation Raman instrument that offers higher sensitivity while also being compact, consuming low power, and exhibiting multifunctionality with microscopic measurement capabilities. Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) based on plasmonic enhancement can enhance a standard Raman signal, particularly from the top surface layer, by $\sim 10^{12}$ times [3]. Raman signal enhancement in SERS occurs when molecules bind to metallic nanostructures, leading to surface plasmon resonance [3]. As discussed in the recent review in reference [4], for planetary missions in particular, SERS may be useful for (1) the search of life on planetary bodies, (2) biological detection in low-earth orbit CubeSat missions, (3) monitoring the health of the astronauts in space stations and shuttles, (4) detecting hazardous contaminants airborne during space flight.

1.1. Previous literature: Earth laboratory studies of SERS using liquids have previously been carried out to detect biological materials on Martian regolith under simulated conditions. Dunn et al. [5], in 2007, explored the use of silver nanoparticles to detect biomolecules, such as amino acids and proteins, at low concentrations of $\sim 10^{-12}$ Molar (picomolar) in olivine rock. The work of Muniz-Miranda et al. [6] followed this in 2010, using silver nanoparticles to investigate the interaction of DNA bases, particularly Adenine, at nanomolar concentrations with pyroxene rocks. The works of Caporali et al. [7][8] followed this in 2011 and 2012, where they used silver and gold nanoparticles and investigated the presence of Adenine at nanomolar concentrations in evaporite materials and Martian meteorites under simulated conditions. The work of Whitaker et al. [9] followed in 2021, in which SERS substrates based on silver and gold nanoparticles were developed to maximize SERS interactions between the substrates and organic molecules embedded in Martian

geological materials. The works in [5]-[9] mainly used silver and gold nanoparticles and essentially focused on two key laboratory experimental processes to ensure SERS enhancement. The first method, drop-casting, involves depositing a colloidal solution of gold or silver nanoparticles onto a rock simulant, enabling plasmonic enhancement of Raman signals. But this often results in non-uniform SERS due to uneven spreading and nanoparticle aggregation. In contrast, the second technique, grinding the rock into a fine powder, involves mixing it with metal nanoparticles in a microfluidic chamber. This allows direct, controlled interaction between biomolecules and nanoparticles, yielding more uniform and reproducible SERS enhancement.

However, significant challenges exist for rover missions, as described below. As discussed in [4], these methods are not suitable for SERS in space due to the requirement for liquid colloids. On an actual planetary surface, without human intervention, it is not possible to grind a target sample in situ and prepare a nanoparticle-containing solution in the proper proportions. Similarly, it becomes ineffective to drop-cast a nanoparticle colloidal solution and expect spatially uniform SERS enhancement while also facing frequent erosion, freezing, and ineffective drops. Additional challenges, as discussed in [4], include the need to preserve nanoparticles for longer durations if the mission itself lasts several years, which therefore requires consumables to be loaded onto a rover during a planetary mission.

2. Proposed efforts: In this presentation, we describe the specific techniques to implement SERS for planetary rover missions, which address the above-mentioned challenges. The first one is based on laser-induced forward transfer (LIFT) of nanoparticles onto a planetary surface, and the second is based on patterned metallic nanoholes; both are considered the best practical solutions for implementing SERS with the largest enhancement factor for planetary rover missions. Both methods eliminate the need for a liquid use. Based on a previous NASA project, the team has developed a compact Raman instrument [10-12] that is now being further developed for SERS studies. The compact spectroscopic optical head is shown in Figure 1(a), with further details described in a previous work [10].

Figure 1. (a) Compact spectroscopic optical head, (b) LIFT method, (c) plasmonic nanohole technique.

2.1. Method 1: LIFT: As shown in Figure 1(b), in this technique, a flexible substrate is used, which is coated with a thin film of a metal ($\sim 25 - 100$ nm) such as silver or gold. A pulsed laser with a wavelength in the near-infrared range (~ 1064 nm) is used to ablate the thin metallic film. Upon ablation, spherical nanoparticles (~ 10 s of nm size) of the metal are formed, which deposit on the planetary surface. A certain degree of uniformity in the diameter of the particles is achieved based on the medium (air/vacuum) in which the experiment is performed. The use of a 1064 nm wavelength allows most substrates to remain transparent to the laser beam, affecting only the thin metallic film, preventing substrate ablation and subsequent contamination of the planetary surface with anything other than metallic nanoparticles. The use of a laser allows control over the location where nanoparticles can be deposited, while avoiding the need to preserve the particles during flight as they are formed in situ. With LIFT, spatially uniform and controlled hotspots of nanoparticles are generated in situ on rock surfaces. Our recent preliminary SERS results in the laboratory with 785 nm Raman excitation have reported a $\sim 10^3$ -fold enhancement with olivine, a planetary mineral.

2.1. Method 2: Plasmonic nanoholes: As shown in Figure 1(c), this technique involves the use of a regular array of nanoholes (diameter $\sim 150 - 200$ nm, and center-to-center spacing between holes $\sim 400 - 500$ nm) prepared by etching through the thickness of a thin metallic film (thickness $\sim 25 - 50$ nm). A glass substrate supports the metallic film. This device, the metallic

nanohole array supported on the substrate, acts as a plasmonic substrate that is placed on top of a planetary surface. For Raman measurements, the laser is probed from the side of the transparent substrate, which passes through the holes towards the planetary surface, and the Raman signal is collected in the backscattering geometry. The dimensions of the hole array determine the wavelength of plasmonic resonance. When the laser and Raman wavelengths match the plasmonic resonance, the holes enable extraordinary transmission (EOT) and an enhanced surface field, leading to SERS. Simulations in Comsol (WaveOptics) reveal that an EOT > 3 is possible in the near-infrared wavelengths using ~ 200 nm-diameter holes spaced by ~ 450 nm, etched into an Au thin film. The use of near-infrared wavelengths avoids fluorescence interference and is suitable for SERS in planetary exploration.

3. Conclusions: The new techniques are described for using plasmonic nanostructures on planetary surfaces, circumventing the current limitations in implementing SERS for space use. The first technique involves LIFT, which generates in situ spatially controlled and spatially uniform nanoparticles. The second technique uses plasmonic nanohole arrays, which further eliminate the need to search for hotspots (with nanoparticles). Recent results using both techniques will be presented.

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